

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A478

13 September 1996

OXICOA — TACIA

ADDENDUM

The correct dates for each of the flights
are as follows:-

475	9 September 1996
476	10 September 1996
477	11 September 1996
478	13 September 1996
479	16 September 1996
480	17 September 1996
481	19 September 1996

TACIA OXICOA AUG-SEPT 96 Flight Summary

Prepared by: Andrew Kaye and Hannah Richer

[1] A475 9/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 1 2 hr 40 min

A short test flight for the chemistry instrumentation was carried out. The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). After initial concerns about the NO background, the NO_x instrument was found to operate satisfactorily on the two available channels (NO and NO₂).

An anticyclone centred to the west of the UK provided possible TACIA type weather. However, delays, due to incomplete airworthiness certification, meant that there was insufficient time to search for plumes from the UK. However, a small local plume was encountered in the Bristol Channel (51.36N, 4.12E).

Data from this flight could possibly be used to validate emission data from South Wales.

[2] A476 10/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 2 4 hr 30 min

Instruments performed as in the previous test flight: The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). The NO background had improved and the NO_x instrument was generally found to operate well on the two channels (NO and NO₂). However, on reaching maximum altitude difficulties were encountered on controlling the flow rate in the NO₂ channel.

A persistent anticyclone centred to the west of the UK again provided TACIA type conditions. However, delays, due to instrument requirements, meant that there was limited time to search for plumes from the UK. However, cross wind runs were carried out at an interval of approximately 60 miles along the SW coast. Trajectory analysis is to be carried out to determine whether the same air mass was sampled twice. However, no particularly notable plumes could be distinguished from the ozone, carbon monoxide and formaldehyde data. However, useful background information was obtained.

[3] A477 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 00 min

The presence of an occluded frontal system over Norway/North Sea facilitated the study of three different airmasses.

Profiles were successfully flown on both sides of the warm front, but there was not sufficient time to travel to the northern edge of the cold frontal surface. However the lowest levels of the second stack may have been north of the front.

Ozone, formaldehyde and PAN instruments worked well, but the CO background problem was not corrected and the NO_x NO₂ channel flow problem had not been resolved.

[4] A478 11/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 3 2 hr 56 min

Thursday 12 September was used to install the NO_y converters and rectify the CO instrument. The CO work was successful. However the NO_y converters took longer than expected to complete. This resulted in a delayed take off.

Although primarily a TACIA instrument test flight the opportunity was taken to characterise the Arctic Maritime air mass over the North Sea. This effectively completed the work started on A477.

The chemistry kit performed as well as could be expected given the reduced warm up

times available. The ozone pump switched off unexpectedly during the flight which caused a loss of data until the problem was identified.

[5] A479 11/9/96 TACIA 5 hr 40 min

There was a high pressure centred over the North Sea on this day which gave rise to continental outflow in the south-west approaches.

A very successful trial of the TACIA flying pattern, with two stacks being flown to sample continental air. A double inversion (875 and 950 mbar) was identified effectively capping pollutants and isolating them from the ocean surface sinks. Elevated levels of aerosol, CO (170 ppb), NO (40 ppt), NO₂ (400 ppt) and O₃ (65 ppb) were noted in this layer. Another interesting parcel of air was also sampled at higher altitudes (6 - 8 km). This air parcel was characterised by high levels of CO and aerosol. All the chemistry instrumentation performed well and the flight will provide a valuable contribution to the TACIA experiment.

[6] A480 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 04 min

An anticyclone was centred to the north of the North Sea, such that continental plumes from northern Europe were reaching southern England across the North Sea. The same anticyclone was investigated during flight A479, at which time the high was centred over the UK.

The aim of this flight was to characterise air parcels within the anticyclone: both air parcels with recent continental influence and those with mainly marine back trajectories were studied. The highest pollutant concentrations of the campaign were measured during this flight in the boundary layer near Boscombe Down and in the marine boundary layer in the southern North Sea.

The marine boundary layer was distinct from the rest of the troposphere by a low level inversion. A slightly higher inversion was also apparent in profiles carried out north of 54 N. Interestingly, the seemingly typical vertical structure was not found in the southern North Sea: only the marine inversion was present.

A plume was encountered in the marine boundary layer at the first sampling region and elevated NO_x, NO_y and CO were observed with a corresponding decrease in ozone, indicating recent anthropogenic inputs. Profiles throughout the lowest 6000 ft of the atmosphere, whilst travelling northward, indicated some chemically aged parcels of air with elevated ozone, CO and NO_y. Haze layers were also visible. However, most of the air was generally clean. Further North, haze layers were less frequent, but layers with elevated ozone were still apparent. Elevated CO with a corresponding decrease in ozone indicated some recent pollution in the marine boundary layer at 57.2 N and 0.8 E.

All the chemistry instruments performed well during the flight. In particular, the peroxide measurements were found to show similar features to the calculated peroxide. Pitch, roll and yaw manoeuvres were carried out in order to test the NO_x inlets: preliminary results indicated that there were no large effects.

[7] A481 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight/NO_x test 6 hr 16 min

An attempt was made at an airmass characterization flight. However, within an hour of take off, the peroxide and CO instruments had failed completely and the NO_x was only functioning at 50%. After consultation with the instrument operators it was decided that useful tests could still be carried with the operational NO_x channels and the flight plan was changed to a NO_x test flight. Several NILU and MRF bottles were also filled for analysis of hydrocarbons and possibly CO.

However, it is interesting to note that, at one point, air of stratospheric origin was encountered: we were frustrated by the lack of a complete suite of instruments. Recently polluted air and air which was chemically aged, as indicated by ratios of NO_x/NO_y and ozone, were both sampled. Useful data on emissions from north eastern Europe may have been gained.

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 478

DATE: 13 109 / 96

Take off : 12:30

Landing : 15:25

Aircraft Scientist	: A KAYE + M RICHER	Captain	: FLt Lt M PURSE
Flight Leader	: D PERCIVAL	Co-pilot	: FLt Lt C WILLIAMS
Others	2) : M PICHERING	Navigator	: MR E HEATON (RAF RET)
	0 ₃ : S KENT	Engineer	: M. ENA K QUICK
NORT	H DEWEY / S BAGHITTE	Loadmaster	: FLt Lt J CANNING
CO	S KESSLER / K GERRIG		
H ₂ O ₂	B BANDY / L GARDINAS		
BOTTLE	D TIDDEMAN		

Trials Instructions TACIA / ACSOË : MRF 13
 Operating area : NORTH SEA

General synoptic situation

TIME : 12

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<p style="text-align: center;">2 1 1</p>	<p>Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 of 2 2 of 2 1 1</p>	<p>Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)</p>
	<p>SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 3</p>	<p>Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">\</p>	<p>Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track</p>

FLIGHT REPORT A478 13/09/96 TACIA

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading
12:30:35				TAKE OFF BOSCOMBE DOWN		
12:55:33	(15)	13:15:53	(16)	Transit to North Sea via Daventry Corridor Run 1	FL150	015° Calibrations 250 kt IAS
13:18:45	(17)	13:28:38	(18)	Profile 1	FL150 FL050	060° 1000'/min
13:28:38	(18)	13:38:22	(19)	P 1 cont	FL050 50 ft	060° 500'/min Sea State 7
13:47:47	(20)	14:02:01	(21)	Run 2	FL090	280°
14:03 28	(22)	14:20:01	(23)	Run 3	FL090	085°
14:22:27	(24)	14:40:01	(25)	Run 4	FL120	270°
14:42:12	(26)	14:57:13	(27)	Run 5	FL120	195° Calibrations 250 tk IAS
				Transit to Boscombe		
15:24:28				LAND AT Boscombe Down		
15:29:01				Data off. Shut down at 51°09.88N 001°44.66W		

A478 13-SEP-96 Height time series

Sortie Brief: TACIA - Instrument Test Flight

Sortie Objective: To test the NO_y channel of the NO_xy instrument and also determine chemical characteristics of an Arctic maritime air mass.

Operational Area: North Sea.

Weather conditions: Avoid areas of cloud and precipitation where possible.

Flight Pattern:

1. Depart Boscombe Down (12:00 local) maintaining altitude at 3000ft until wet chemistry instruments are checked.
2. Profile ascent to FL150 maintain horizontal run for 20 minutes.
3. Profile descent into operational area (as normal).
- ~~4. Sawtooth in and out of boundary layer for 30 minutes.~~
5. Carry out racetrack perpendicular to wind direction, above boundary layer. Reciprocal run turning into wind to avoid C130 exhaust (40 mins total).
- ~~6. Repeat [5], at different level.~~
- ~~7. Left hand orbit followed by a right hand orbit (above boundary layer).~~
- ~~8. Three straight and level runs, five minutes each, at different angles of attack (above boundary layer).~~
- ~~9. Two straight and level runs, five minutes each, crabbing left then right (above boundary layer).~~
- ~~10. Fifteen minutes in boundary layer for instrument calibration.~~
11. Transit to Boscombe Down, maintaining constant altitude (above boundary layer) for 15 minutes. Arriving Boscombe Down at 16:30 local.

Other requirements: Constant pressurisation on horizontal runs (not required for [7,8,9]).

MP P1
C Williams P2
EM N
KA E
SC LM

AIRCRAFT FLYING PROGRAMME

DATE 13th September
FTI MRF 13 TACIA

FLIGHT NO A478

Aircraft scientist A Kaye
Flight leader D Percival
Cloud physics M Pickering
PAN/Ozone J Kent
NOXY K Dewey / S Baguitte
CO S Kessler / K Gerbig
Peroxide B Bandy / L Gardinas
Bottle Sampler D Tiddeman
+ H Richer

Pre-flight clearance D Boyd / D Findley dep 0730L
FTOs depart F'boro 0745L

Briefing 0900L Take off 1200L Return 1625L

Press RETURN for next display (H for help) TODAY 12-SEP-1996 15:46

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A473

Date: 13 07 96

A/S Name: KATE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for³.....

2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period INDEF

3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project IACIA

4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? INDEF

5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished? OR TUE NIGHT .

6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?

7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: *Keisei/Tacira* Date: *18/9/1966*

Aircraft Scientist: *A Koye & H. Richter*

Flight No: *A478* Page 1 of 2

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
<i>12:37:13</i>		<i>Transit</i>	<i>6.0</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>357</i>	<i>51.55</i>	<i>-1.65</i>	<i>Small cum field. Clear above.</i>	
<i>12:46:21</i>		<i>Transit</i>	<i>10.1</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>46</i>	<i>52.12</i>	<i>-1.41</i>	<i>5/8 High cum layer.</i>	
<i>12:55:34</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>R1s</i>	<i>150</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>52.41</i>	<i>-0.71</i>	<i>4/8 Broken Sc. sheet. Clear above</i>	
<i>13:00:47</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>R1</i>	<i>151</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>52.74</i>	<i>-0.61</i>	<i>Broken Sc. below clear Above.</i>	
<i>13:07:42</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>R1</i>	<i>151</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>53.31</i>	<i>-0.46</i>	<i>6/8 Sc. sheet below clear above</i>	
<i>13:15:52</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>R1e</i>	<i>150</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>359</i>	<i>53.86</i>	<i>-0.39</i>	<i>Broken Sc below. 1010</i>	
<i>13:22:00</i>		<i>P1</i>	<i>150</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>36</i>	<i>54.00</i>	<i>-0.11</i>	<i>3/8 Broken Sc sheets over sea.</i>	
<i>13:28:28</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>P1</i>	<i>4.7</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>67</i>	<i>54.16</i>	<i>0.60</i>	<i>Change to 1000 5000 ft/min.</i>	
<i>12:31:44</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>P1</i>	<i>32</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>61</i>	<i>57.20</i>	<i>0.82</i>	<i>High layer with rough sea below.</i>	
<i>12:38:22</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>P1e</i>	<i>50.1</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>A</i>			<i>1018 sea state 7</i>	
								<i>FL 90 & 150</i>	
<i>13:47:44</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>R2e</i>	<i>90</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>272</i>	<i>54.36</i>	<i>1.94</i>	<i>5/8 Cu below clear and sunny above.</i>	

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A47D Date: 130996 User: CHEMISTRY
Interactive by: D PERCIVAL
Date: 17 0496

Renav

KALMAN FILTERING CHOSEN

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : ~~Profile~~ Whole flight ~~Other~~

$$a = - 0.3482E + 01$$

$$b = + 0.2098E - 02$$

$$c = + 0.6972E - 06$$

LWC

Ch

Heimann / Barnes

Ch

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A478 Date: 130996

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1027	REF +	5	0567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2855			Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	0000	2.0 F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	2109	3.0 F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0000	/		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3871	1004	1002	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3980	1004			
	A/S	9	0074	20		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	1806	589	592		
	UP2S	82	1528	276	309		
	UIRS	83	0650	-273	1558		
	UP1Z	84	0152	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	0146	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	0648	2002		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2457	19		As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2480	18	17.5	As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0473	130	129		
	LP2S	92	0401	.65	63		
	LIRS	93	0123	-388	1559		
	LP1Z	94	0151	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	0155	/		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	0112	2002		Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2436	19		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2403	21	17.4	As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0000	/		As IAT	
	J/W	42	0996	/ 001		As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47	0000				
	HYGR	58	2595	3.6	3.7		
	HYCC	59	0721	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	4095			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	4095				
	DTF	10	0614	17			
	DTC	11	6		17.2		
	NDTF	23	0185	16		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	6				
	INCT	48	4095				
HEIM	GEN	149	2635			less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2212	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	0169	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0101	/			
	O3P	106	2005	947		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1537	/			
	PATC	142	2391				
	O3F	114	1027				

150 HCHO 0326
151 ORGP 0001
152 H2O2 0003
154 CC 0017
155 PHN 1283
156 POC 1296

195 FIFL 1088
196 FIPR 1374
197 P2FL 1508
198 FIPR 1580
0175 URS 296
176 UIMP 892
177 URTS 000

179 URTS 968
180 NBS 875
181 URTS 983
182 NRBS 1008
183 NMM 1022
184 NTS 1041

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1107	FL NO	1	Hex	0478	A478	✓	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0110	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0815	110815	✓	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	11→12	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				4	0	9	5
	LATC	160	Dec	4044			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4044			Longitude
1109							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: PRE FLIGHT

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1104	TWCD	70	2213	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1302	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0143	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2540	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2266	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2071	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2125	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1022	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4099			4095	
	EV1V	170	2043				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3314				
	EVIC	173	3968				
1115	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear /	OFF / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red /		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon ³ NGT		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear /	OFF / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red /		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon ³ WT		

Flight Leader's ~~Pre~~ In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A47P Date: 130996

Page...2 of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1237	REF +	5	567			Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2855			Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	1279	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1502	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095	FL100		As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	2688	100	FL100	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3998	983			
	A/S	9	2605	256	256	As ASI	0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	2063	680	646		
	UP2S	82	1627	308	343		
	UIRS	83	0864	-230	1558		
	UP1Z	84	154	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	147	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	854	/	3002	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2644	9		As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2664	8	12.4	As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000	/		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	530	149	281		
	LP2S	92	652	130	133		
	LIRS	93	432	-330	1554		
	LP1Z	94	151	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	163	/		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	450	/		Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2748	4		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2750	4	4.3	As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0000	3002		As IAT	
	J/W	42	1021	-0.1		As Indicated	0000
	NEPH	47	XXXX				
	HYGR	58	1203	-21.0	-20 ✓		
	HYCC	59	0758	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	593	-70.3	?	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	921				
	DTF	10	1144	3			
	DTC	11	5		4.2		
	NDTF	23	999	3		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	4095	✓			
HEIM	ECN	140	2492			less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2398	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1343	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	152				
	O3P	106	1964	930.6		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	779				
	PRTC	142	2343				
1308	O3F	114	1831				

150 HCHO 267
151 ORGP 0008
152 H2O2 0053
154 CU 0108
185 PLIN 1425
186 OAC 1430
187 OAC 1427

195 FFL 1028
146 FPR 1157
197 F2PR 1179
198 F2PR 1239
175 MPRS 510
176 NTMP 1030
177 NRTS 1012

174 NRTS 1115
120 NBS 1032
181 NRTS 1132
182 NRTS 1144
183 NHUM 1159
184 NRTS 1172

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1410	FL NO	1	Hex	0478	A478	✓	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0141	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	212	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	22	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				4	0	9	5
	LATC	160	Dec	618	54.3844	✓	Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0016	1°4.08E	✓	Longitude
1412							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL120.

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1447	TWCD	70	1510	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2516	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1396	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2676	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2246	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	784	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2183	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1014	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095			4095	
	EV1V	170	3480				
	EV2V	171	3136				
	NPWR	172	2701				
	EVIC	173	4019				
1453	EV2C	174	4007				

v55

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

[Handwritten marks]

Flight No A 478#1..... Date 13.09.96..... Page 1 of 1.....

Video Tape	
No. A 478#1	
Ends 1539	
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	51°09.88N	51°09.88N
Long	001°44.65W	001°44.61W
Time	093111	093143
Status	OK	OK ALIGN

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
0741.29				DATA	OK				
1212.36				SET TO NAV					
1230.35				TAKE OFF	Boxcar DE.				
				Climb directly / J Target					
				START	RUN 1		-CALIB		
1255.33	15	FL150	1013	015	250	-8.2	-23.6	OFF	013/23
				END	RUN 1				
1315.53	16	FL150	1013	005	180	-9.6	-17.8	OFF	003/20
				START	P1				1000/m
1318.45	17	FL150	1013	060	180	-9.4	15.8	OFF	006/19
				CONT	P1				5000/m
1328.38	18	FL050	1013	075	185	-0.1	-0.3	OFF	013/14
				END	P1				
1338.22	19	5000	1018	060	180	12.9	7.6	OFF	357/13
				Hiway	Col P 07				SS=7
				START	RUN 2				
1347.47	20	FL090	1013	280	180	-3.6	-21.2	OFF	358/16
							INTERESTING CHANGE IN DP		HREC
				END	RUN 2				03
1402.01	21	FL090	1013	280	180	-3.5	-34.1	OFF	006/18

* Research Flight

Video Tape	
No.	A-47211
Ends	1539
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	54.19.23N	54.1878N
Long	0° 52.93E	00° 47.70E
Time	135850	135940
Status	OK	NAV.

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y/n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y/n
SATCOM sending pos reports	☒ y/n

100Cr. CRG

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
				Revised		Run -			
		F		START		RUN 3			
140328	22	FL090	1013	085	180	-3.4	-34.5	OFF	014/15
141116	change to DFC.								
					END	RUN 3			
142001	23	FL090	1013	085	180	-2.9	-2	OFF	040/13
					START	R4			
142227	24	FL120	1013	280	180	-6.2	-33.13	OFF	004/18.
142320	vid back to FFC.								
					END	R4			
144001	25	FL120	1013	0270	180	-4.2	-11.7	OFF	006/20
					START	R5			
144212	26	FL120	1013	295	250	-3.8	-10.4	OFF	005/21
					END	R5			
145713	27	FL120	1013	195	250	-3.1	-13.4	OFF	006/20
				TRANSIT		NOISE			
1452428				LAND		AZE ² .			
				HOLD		510988N			
						001 44 2600			
152901				DATA		OFF			

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A 478**.....

Project **TACUT./ACSOE**.....

Date **13.09.96**.....

Tape No **AH78 #1** User **CHEMISTRY**.....

Retention Period **INDEF**.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
1239	0220	FFC	Started Tape In climb out
1255 33 131553		FFC	Run 1 FL 150
131845 133822		"	Prof 1 FL150 → 50 ^{ft}
134747 140201		"	Run 2 FL 090
140320 142001		FFC DFC @ 141116	Run 3 FL 090
142227 144001		DFC FFC @ 142320	Run 4 FL 120
144212 145713		FFC	Run 5 FL 120
1524			LAND @ BOLCOMBE
1524			TAPE OFF

FT LDR

INPUT WEIGHT & FUEL SUMMARY

Computed for Met Research Flight by C F P

Max TOW = 155000 lbs Max LW = 135000 lbs
 ZFW = 96000 lbs
 Ramp Fuel = 33000 lbs
 Start/Taxy = 1000 lbs
 Diversion = 1000 lbs
 Overhead = 5500 lbs
 Hold FF = 4500 lbs
 Contingency = 5 %
 Extra Fuel = 0 lbs
 Hercules-W2 MEAN Computed

Weather

Dep: EGDM	Elev: 00407'	Des: EGDM	Elev: 00407'
R/W: OAT: QNH :		R/W: OAT: QNH :	
W/V: QFE :		W/V: QFE :	
Wx: SALT:		Wx: SALT:	
Cloud:		Cloud:	

From EGDM To EGDM C/S Crew Date 13 09 96

ATC

WPT	Lvl	W/V	ISA	TkT	TkM	Dr	TAS	GrS	DIS	EET	ETA	ATA	TET	FU	Rmg	FF(k)	DTG
EGDM															32000		598
10ML05	ASC	001/20	+5	230	234	-5	180	192	11	3			0.03	400	31600	8.0	587
FFA	30	001/20	+5	009	014	+1	250	230	39	10			0.13	1119	30481	6.6	548
DTYW	60	001/40	+5	071	076	+9	240	223	53	14			0.27	1426	29055	6.0	495
DTYE	100	001/40	+5	358	002	-0	305	265	25	6			0.33	642	28413	6.8	470
WIT	120	001/40	+5	351	355	-2	260	221	14	4			0.37	380	28033	6.0	456
54N0##	150	001/47	+4	004	008	+0	310	263	84	19			0.56	2124	25909	6.7	372
STRUN1	70	001/27	+4	075	079	+7	220	211	84	24			1.20	1991	23918	5.0	288
ENRUN1	50	001/27	+5	267	270	-8	190	190	70	22			1.42	1879	22039	5.1	218
LOITER										40			2.22	3333	18706	5.0	218
GAM	80	001/36	+5	210	215	-5	210	241	67	17			2.39	1529	17177	5.5	151
DTYE	140	001/36	+5	161	166	+2	313	347	57	10			2.49	1068	16109	6.5	94
DTYW	100	001/36	+5	182	186	-0	308	344	25	4			2.53	494	15615	6.8	69
EGDM	50	001/20	+5	226	230	-4	210	224	69	22			3.15	1694	13921	5.5	0
Diversion																	
										Totals	598	191					
EGDL	50	C-30	+5	336	340	+0	210	180	23	8			3.19	703	13218	5.5	0

FUEL SUMMARY lbs
 Start/Taxy : 1000 T/O Fuel : 32000
 Plan Fuel : 18079 Plan Fuel : 18079
 Diversion : 1000 Actual Reserve : 13921
 Min Overhead : 5500 Hold Fuel Flow : 4500
 Contingency : 904 Rsv Endurance : 3.05
 Extra Fuel : 0 Flt Plan Time : 3.11
 Reqd Start Fuel: 26483 Total Endurance: 6.16

WEIGHT SUMMARY lbs
 ZFW : 96000
 Ramp Fuel : 33000
 Ramp Weight : 129000
 Take Off Weight: 128000
 Landing Weight : 109921

(c) RJCVC 1991

WAYPOINTS

OBSERVATIONS

WAYPOINTS	OBSERVATIONS
EGDM 00407' N5109.5 W00144.3	①
10ML05 N5102.2 W00158.2	②
FFA 081X N5140.9 W00147.8	③
DTYW DTCORW N5158.0 W00027.0	④
DTYE DTCORE N5223.0 W00026.0	⑤
WIT 123X N5236.4 W00029.8	⑥
54N0## N5400.0 W00020.0	⑦
STRUN1 N5420.0 E00200.0	⑧
ENRUN1 UK N5415.0 W00000.0	⑨
GAM 112.80 N5316.9 W00056.7	⑩
DTYE DTCORE N5223.0 W00026.0	
DTYW DTCORW N5158.0 W00027.0	
EGDM 00407' N5109.5 W00144.3	
EGDL 00513' N5130.6 W00159.4	

DATE 13/9/96

TI MRF TACIA

NAV HEATON (14)

AIRFIELD Base P1016

AIRFIELD Base 1016

R/WOS W/V 350/173 TEMP +20 ONH 1019 OFF 1004

R/WOS W/V 010/174 TEMP +17 ONH 1019 OFF 1004

WX NW

WX LL NO 24500

ATC CL 3000 1557

ATC CL 02 UN

T/O TIME 1230

LAND TIME

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1234	006								3000 Star Fl60	—
125533	010	φ	250	233	300	01/45	FL150	1013	NS2244 W000434	RUN 1
131555						000/40	FL150	✓	NS3503 W00023.6	END RUN 1
131845	066	95	213	188	232	012/34	↓	1010	NS3565 W000617.8	ST P1
133825	060					357/30	50'	1017	NS418.1 E00116.6	END P1
✓								1013	↗ FL90	
134840	272	90	211	181	209	003/29	FL90	1013	NS4218 E001567	ST RUN 2
140200						007/32	✓	✓	NS419.2 E00032.1	END RUN 2
140326	088	95	196	180	205	016/29	90	✓	NS4203 E00032.2	ST RUN 3
140500							90		NS422.1 E00208.3	END RUN 3
✓									↗ FL120	
142226	271	90	223	180	220	003/35	FL120	1013	NS423.7 E00200.2	RUN 4
144000						009/40	FL120	✓	NS412.7 E000069	END RUN 4
144212	188	φ	300	258	315	007/40	FL120	✓	NS4029 W000000	ST RUN 5
145712						008/40	✓		NS2377 W00025.2	END RUN 5
									↓ FL100	
									↘ 20 1662	
									↘ NO	
									CLW16 ↓ 3000	

9000 Heat

1478 13-SEP-96 13:42:18 019 Ω 54.35 1.62 FR P

HDG deg T 84.	SPR mb 803.	PHGT kft 6.3	TAS knots 196.	TAT C -0.7	DEW C -18.9	WIND deg m/s 014/14
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EE -GT 1.000.00 m H2O2 MP 0.10 RPB MOD H2O2 0.000.00
 0.00 0.50 1.00 1.50 2.00 2.50

A ELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A478

13-SEP-96

13:37:33

018 Ω 54.30

1.23 FR P

HDG degT 59.	SPR mb 1005.	PHGT kft 0.2	TAS knots 184.	TAT C 11.9	DEW C 7.4	WIND deg m/s 355/16
--------------------	--------------------	--------------------	----------------------	------------------	-----------------	---------------------------

REF -GT 0.00 25.00 50.00 75.00 100.00 125.00
 0.00 25.00 50.00 75.00 100.00 125.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A478 13-SEP-96 13:21:09 017 2 54.02 -0.05 FR P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEM C	WIND deg m/s
56.	631.	12.5	224.	-4.4	-13.5	016/21

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			WIDEO	HELP

HDG deg T	SPR m/b	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEM C	WIND deg m/s
11.	570.	15.1	311.	-9.1	-18.8	009/21

SECRET

HDG deg T 11.	SPR mb 571.	PHGT kft 15.1	TAS knots 311.	TAT C -9.0	DEW C -20.5	WIND deg m/s 010/21
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A SELECT	B PARAS	C AREA	D ZOOM	E	F	G MENU	H HELP
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A478 13-SEP-96 14:46:18 020 00 03.00 -0.0111

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEM C	WIND deg m/s
193.	646.	12.0	311.	-4.1	-10.1	008/22

-303 0.12 000 -303 0.11

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
LECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			WIDEO	HELP

A478 13-SEP-96 12:59:24 015 52.68 -0.00 FK C

HDS	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
heat	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
10.	570.	15.1	312.	-9.0	-19.4	012/22

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A478 13-SEP-96 13:01:09 015 52.80 -0.61 FR P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEM C	WIND deg m/s
11.	570.	15.1	312.	-9.0	-19.5	012/22

-202 202 0.12 0.22 0.32

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			WIDEO	HELP

A478 13-SEP-96 13:08:48 015 Ω 53.37 -0.45 FR P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEM C	WIND deg m/s
7.	570.	15.1	310.	-9.5	-18.2	009/21

CO MR 221.00 38.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			WIDED	HELP

A478 13-SEP-96 13:46:33 019 54.34 2.04 FR

HDG degT 38.	SPR mb 723.	PHGT kft 9.0	TAS knts 210.	TAT C -3.4	DEW C -16.2	WIND deg m/s 002/16
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

HDG deg T 74.	SPR mb 921.	PHGT kft 2.6	TAS knots 191.	TAT C 5.7	DEW C 1.5	WIND deg m/s 002/17
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A SELECT	B CHEN	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A478

13-SEP-96

13:16:48

016 Ω

53.88

-0.39 FR P

HDG degT 359.	SPR mb 571.	PHGT kft 15.0	TAS knts 230.	TAT C -9.7	DEW C -16.4	WIND deg m/s 000/19
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A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A478 13-SEP-96 13:38:42 019 54.32 1.31 AS P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
53.	1002.	0.3	182.	11.8	7.5	358/15

PRES HGT 95.98 m OZONE MR 32.62 PPb CO MR 91.00 PPb
 0.00 33.33 56.67 100.00 133.33 156.67 10000.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
CECT	NUM	700M				VIDEO	

TSXX 007 14 SEP 1996

TSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 14 SEP 1996

Fig. Stereographic projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original

MET OFFICE FAX F 28 ** TOTAL PAGE. 001

PAGE. 001

10 4806

FROM MET IT OPS BRACKNELL

13 SEP '96 04:05

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INTERVALS

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

13 SEP '96 04:21

13 SEP '96 04:21

NOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
 DIAL PPN RATE
 RESSURE AT MSL

SNOW
 CONVECTIVE
 DYNAMIC

.03 .1 .5 1.0 MM/HR AT VT

TOTAL ACCUMULATION

RAINFALL IN MM DURING THE 6 HOURS ENDING AT VT

...:1 10 .5 A:10 B:11 C:12 0:13 E:15 F:15 G:16 H:17 J:18 N:19 L:20 M:21 N:22 P:23 Q:24 R:25 S:29 T:30 U:30 V:39 W:40 X:44 Y:55 Z:59 T:60-6N Z:65 AND OVER

FACIT 4-UP 13 SEP '96 13:48

122 13 SEP 1996

LERHICK 03005 AT 112		DE BILT 06260	
10	340	19	355
15	350	20	350
20	320	25	360
25	320	30	010
30	330	35	005
35	330	40	013
40	330	45	012
45	330	50	010
50	330	55	355
55	310	60	355
60	310	65	340
65	310	70	340
70	310	75	340
75	310	80	340
80	310	85	340
85	310	90	340
90	310	95	340
95	310	100	340
100	310	105	340
105	310	110	340
110	310	115	340
115	310	120	340
120	310	125	340
125	310	130	340
130	310	135	340
135	310	140	340
140	310	145	340
145	310	150	340
150	310	155	340
155	310	160	340
160	310	165	340
165	310	170	340
170	310	175	340
175	310	180	340
180	310	185	340
185	310	190	340
190	310	195	340
195	310	200	340
200	310	205	340
205	310	210	340
210	310	215	340
215	310	220	340
220	310	225	340
225	310	230	340
230	310	235	340
235	310	240	340
240	310	245	340
245	310	250	340
250	310	255	340
255	310	260	340
260	310	265	340
265	310	270	340
270	310	275	340
275	310	280	340
280	310	285	340
285	310	290	340
290	310	295	340
295	310	300	340
300	310	305	340
305	310	310	340
310	310	315	340
315	310	320	340
320	310	325	340
325	310	330	340
330	310	335	340
335	310	340	340
340	310	345	340
345	310	350	340
350	310	355	340
355	310	360	340
360	310	365	340
365	310	370	340
370	310	375	340
375	310	380	340
380	310	385	340
385	310	390	340
390	310	395	340
395	310	400	340
400	310	405	340
405	310	410	340
410	310	415	340
415	310	420	340
420	310	425	340
425	310	430	340
430	310	435	340
435	310	440	340
440	310	445	340
445	310	450	340
450	310	455	340
455	310	460	340
460	310	465	340
465	310	470	340
470	310	475	340
475	310	480	340
480	310	485	340
485	310	490	340
490	310	495	340
495	310	500	340
500	310	505	340
505	310	510	340
510	310	515	340
515	310	520	340
520	310	525	340
525	310	530	340
530	310	535	340
535	310	540	340
540	310	545	340
545	310	550	340
550	310	555	340
555	310	560	340
560	310	565	340
565	310	570	340
570	310	575	340
575	310	580	340
580	310	585	340
585	310	590	340
590	310	595	340
595	310	600	340
600	310	605	340
605	310	610	340
610	310	615	340
615	310	620	340
620	310	625	340
625	310	630	340
630	310	635	340
635	310	640	340
640	310	645	340
645	310	650	340
650	310	655	340
655	310	660	340
660	310	665	340
665	310	670	340
670	310	675	340
675	310	680	340
680	310	685	340
685	310	690	340
690	310	695	340
695	310	700	340
700	310	705	340
705	310	710	340
710	310	715	340
715	310	720	340
720	310	725	340
725	310	730	340
730	310	735	340
735	310	740	340
740	310	745	340
745	310	750	340
750	310	755	340
755	310	760	340
760	310	765	340
765	310	770	340
770	310	775	340
775	310	780	340
780	310	785	340
785	310	790	340
790	310	795	340
795	310	800	340
800	310	805	340
805	310	810	340
810	310	815	340
815	310	820	340
820	310	825	340
825	310	830	340
830	310	835	340
835	310	840	340
840	310	845	340
845	310	850	340
850	310	855	340
855	310	860	340
860	310	865	340
865	310	870	340
870	310	875	340
875	310	880	340
880	310	885	340
885	310	890	340
890	310	895	340
895	310	900	340
900	310	905	340
905	310	910	340
910	310	915	340
915	310	920	340
920	310	925	340
925	310	930	340
930	310	935	340
935	310	940	340
940	310	945	340
945	310	950	340
950	310	955	340
955	310	960	340
960	310	965	340
965	310	970	340
970	310	975	340
975	310	980	340
980	310	985	340
985	310	990	340
990	310	995	340
995	310	1000	340
1000	310	1005	340
1005	310	1010	340
1010	310	1015	340
1015	310	1020	340
1020	310	1025	340
1025	310	1030	340
1030	310	1035	340
1035	310	1040	340
1040	310	1045	340
1045	310	1050	340
1050	310	1055	340
1055	310	1060	340
1060	310	1065	340
1065	310	1070	340
1070	310	1075	340
1075	310	1080	340
1080	310	1085	340
1085	310	1090	340
1090	310	1095	340
1095	310	1100	340
1100	310	1105	340
1105	310	1110	340
1110	310	1115	340
1115	310	1120	340
1120	310	1125	340
1125	310	1130	340
1130	310	1135	340
1135	310	1140	340
1140	310	1145	340
1145	310	1150	340
1150	310	1155	340
1155	310	1160	340
1160	310	1165	340
1165	310	1170	340
1170	310	1175	340
1175	310	1180	340
1180	310	1185	340
1185	310	1190	340
1190	310	1195	340
1195	310	1200	340
1200	310	1205	340
1205	310	1210	340
1210	310	1215	340
1215	310	1220	340
1220	310	1225	340
1225	310	1230	340
1230	310	1235	340
1235	310	1240	340
1240	310	1245	340
1245	310	1250	340
1250	310	1255	340
1255	310	1260	340
1260	310	1265	340
1265	310	1270	340
1270	310	1275	340
1275	310	1280	340
1280	310	1285	340
1285	310	1290	340
1290	310	1295	340
1295	310	1300	340
1300	310	1305	340
1305	310	1310	340
1310	310	1315	340
1315	310	1320	340
1320	310	1325	340
1325	310	1330	340
1330	310	1335	340
1335	310	1340	340
1340	310	1345	340
1345	310	1350	340
1350	310	1355	340
1355	310	1360	340
1360	310	1365	340
1365	310	1370	340
1370	310	1375	340
1375	310	1380	340
1380	310	1385	340
1385	310	1390	340
1390	310	1395	340
1395	310	1400	340
1400	310	1405	340
1405	310	1410	340
1410	310	1415	340
1415	310	1420	340
1420	310	1425	340
1425	310	1430	340
1430	310	1435	340
1435	310	1440	340
1440	310	1445	340
1445	310	1450	340
1450	310	1455	340
1455	310	1460	340
1460	310	1465	340
1465	310	1470	340
1470	310	1475	340
1475	310	1480	340
1480	310	1485	340
1485	310	1490	340
1490	310	1495	340
1495	310	1500	340
1500	310	1505	340
1505	310	1510	340
1510	310	1515	

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 13 SEP 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

** TOTAL PAGE.001 **
MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_1 PAGE.001

13 SEP '96 15:45

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A478.TXT

From 15Z 9/ 9/1996 to 15Z 13/ 9/1996

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 27-04-1996 11:55

A478 13-SEP-96

P1 FL150-50 ft(131845-133822)

A478 13-SEP-96 R1 FL150 From 125533-131553 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:02

A478 13-SEP-96 R1 FL150 From 125533-131553 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:03

A478 13-SEP-96 R1 FL150 From 125533-131553 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:03

A478 13-SEP-96 R1 FL150 From 125533-131553 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:03

A478 13-SEP-96 R1 FL150 From 125533-131553 *Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:03*

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 1221
Mean 571.557
Standard dev 0.522811
Max value 573.458
Min value 570.181

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 1221
Mean 264.324
Standard dev 0.381164
Max value 265.239
Min value 263.570

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 1221
Mean 252.375
Standard dev 2.54012
Max value 256.791
Min value 244.625

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 1221
Mean 48.2022
Standard dev 4.79942
Max value 58.1042
Min value 39.1941

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 1221
Mean 17.7986
Standard dev 9.13187
Max value 102.832
Min value 2.00000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 1221
Mean 1.263048e-05
Standard dev 4.413445e-04
Max value 1.542182e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 1221
Mean 4575.40
Standard dev 6.91484
Max value 4593.63
Min value 4550.27

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 1221
Mean 53.1237
Standard dev 0.427437
Max value 53.8262
Min value 52.3886

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 1221
Mean -0.530593
Standard dev 0.102311
Max value -0.401179
Min value -0.730197

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1221
Mean -21.1579
Standard dev 0.795685
Max value -19.4926
Min value -22.7865

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1221
Mean -3.54222
Standard dev 1.33194
Max value -0.206070
Min value -6.29044

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1221
Mean 2.552577e-02
Standard dev 0.507669
Max value 1.26399
Min value -1.01292

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 1221
Mean 21.4885
Standard dev 0.925779
Max value 23.2438
Min value 19.4951

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 9.50420

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 1221
Mean 154.078
Standard dev 12.6147
Max value 162.163
Min value 115.961

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 7.73371

A478 13-SEP-96 P1 FL150-50 ft From 131845-133822 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:08

A478 13-SEP-96 P1 FL150-50 ft From 131845-133822 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 15:08

A478 13-SEP-96 P1 FL150-50 ft From 131845-133822 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:09

A478 13-SEP-96 R2 FL090 From 134747-140201 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:05

A478 13-SEP-96 R2 FL090 From 134747-140201 Plotted 11-01-1996 16:05

A478 13-SEP-96 R2 FL090 From 134747-140201 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:06

A478 13-SEP-96 R2 FL090 From 134747-140201 *Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:06*

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 855
Mean 725.488
Standard dev 0.811316
Max value 726.480
Min value 722.861

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 855
Mean 270.017
Standard dev 0.345940
Max value 270.977
Min value 269.177

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 855
Mean 241.900
Standard dev 5.24800
Max value 253.267
Min value 237.240

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 855
Mean 5.00609
Standard dev 14.3418
Max value 48.4377
Min value 1.000000e-38

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 855
Mean 43.1310
Standard dev 17.7092
Max value 95.1051
Min value 3.00010

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 855
Mean 4.259478e-04
Standard dev 3.457679e-03
Max value 4.597446e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 855
Mean 2730.02
Standard dev 8.85894
Max value 2758.72
Min value 2719.21

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 855
Mean 54.3343
Standard dev 1.644103e-02
Max value 54.3635
Min value 54.3037

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 855
Mean 1.24652
Standard dev 0.406813
Max value 1.95243
Min value 0.543261

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 855
Mean -16.7060
Standard dev 1.45064
Max value -13.8553
Min value -19.8561

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 855
Mean -0.797933
Standard dev 0.757896
Max value 1.15845
Min value -3.15170

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 855
Mean 5.575237e-02
Standard dev 0.329620
Max value 0.940605
Min value -1.16733

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 855
Mean 16.7422
Standard dev 1.45035
Max value 19.8897
Min value 13.9033

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 2.73456

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 855
Mean 106.739
Standard dev 0.937381
Max value 109.158
Min value 103.536

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 265.837

A478 13-SEP-96 R3 FL090 From 140328-142001 Plotted 11-0d-1996 15:22

A478 13-SEP-96 R3 FL090 From 140328-142001 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:22

A478 13-SEP-96 R3 FL090 From 140328-142001 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:22

A478 13-SEP-96 R3 FL090 From 140328-142001 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:22

A478 13-SEP-96 R3 FLO90 From 140328-142001 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:22

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 994
Mean 725.739
Standard dev 0.185439
Max value 726.228
Min value 724.881

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 994
Mean 270.151
Standard dev 0.345798
Max value 270.857
Min value 269.315

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 994
Mean 240.922
Standard dev 4.57448
Max value 252.650
Min value 237.232

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 994
Mean 1.000000e-38
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 1.000000e-38
Min value 1.000000e-38

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 994
Mean 42.9140
Standard dev 16.8936
Max value 93.0938
Min value 5.00016

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 994
Mean 3.642579e-04
Standard dev 2.849444e-03
Max value 2.298723e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 994
Mean 2727.28
Standard dev 2.02243
Max value 2736.64
Min value 2721.95

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 994
Mean 54.3538
Standard dev 7.903200e-03
Max value 54.3686
Min value 54.3385

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 994
Mean 1.32228
Standard dev 0.465136
Max value 2.13042
Min value 0.523038

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 994
Mean -13.6996
Standard dev 1.24423
Max value -10.9131
Min value -16.3279

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 994
Mean -0.981366
Standard dev 0.923857
Max value 1.07308
Min value -4.15160

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 994
Mean -1.264431e-02
Standard dev 0.269595
Max value 1.05960
Min value -0.873901

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 994
Mean 13.7647
Standard dev 1.25447
Max value 16.3407
Min value 11.0251

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 4.09738

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 994
Mean 107.436
Standard dev 1.15174
Max value 110.418
Min value 104.124

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 88.1662

A478 13-SEP-96 R4 FL120 From 142227-144001 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:15

A478 13-SEP-96 R4 FL120 From 142227-144001 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:15

A478 13-SEP-96 R4 FL120 From 142227-144001 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:16

A478 13-SEP-96 R4 FL120 From 142227-144001 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 16:16

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 645.096
 Standard dev 0.319099
 Max value 645.849
 Min value 642.904

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 14.6244
 Standard dev 20.6187
 Max value 47.6853
 Min value 1.000000e-38

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 3649.28
 Standard dev 3.83039
 Max value 3675.62
 Min value 3640.26

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean -21.3051
 Standard dev 0.941687
 Max value -16.8308
 Min value -22.8419

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 21.7254
 Standard dev 1.07336
 Max value 23.6238
 Min value 17.0076

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 10.6486

STATIC TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 268.774
 Standard dev 0.523141
 Max value 269.724
 Min value 266.802

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 32.6262
 Standard dev 18.4000
 Max value 136.226
 Min value 2.00006

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 54.3047
 Standard dev 5.434243e-02
 Max value 54.3961
 Min value 54.2110

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean -4.00584
 Standard dev 1.51817
 Max value -1.25352
 Min value -6.80132

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 113.401
 Standard dev 1.58262
 Max value 116.991
 Min value 110.471

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 247.358
 Standard dev 13.6126
 Max value 262.374
 Min value 227.749

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 4.239373e-04
 Standard dev 3.113908e-03
 Max value 4.201251e-02
 Min value 0.000000

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean 1.06314
 Standard dev 0.554012
 Max value 2.01740
 Min value 0.113976

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1055
 Mean -0.142551
 Standard dev 0.381464
 Max value 0.926498
 Min value -1.35487

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 260.552

A478 13-SEP-96 R5 FL120 From 144212-145713 Plotted 11-01-1996 15:36

A478 13-SEP-96 R5 FL120 From 144212-145713 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:36

A478 13-SEP-96 R5 FL120 From 144212-145713 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:36

A478 13-SEP-96 R5 FL120 From 144212-145713 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:36

A478 13-SEP-96 R5 FL120 From 144212-145713 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 15:37

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 902
Mean 646.747
Standard dev 0.220381
Max value 647.877
Min value 645.143

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 902
Mean 269.821
Standard dev 0.385074
Max value 270.822
Min value 268.919

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 902
Mean 261.032
Standard dev 1.30216
Max value 263.255
Min value 258.209

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 902
Mean 41.9316
Standard dev 1.24497
Max value 45.6679
Min value 38.1755

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 902
Mean 6.64722
Standard dev 3.63888
Max value 21.0041
Min value 0.000000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 902
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 902
Mean 3629.50
Standard dev 2.63893
Max value 3648.72
Min value 3615.97

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 902
Mean 53.3377
Standard dev 0.417104
Max value 54.0595
Min value 52.6176

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 902
Mean -0.208618
Standard dev 0.121370
Max value -2.880605e-03
Min value -0.417258

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 902
Mean -20.4852
Standard dev 0.625631
Max value -19.3029
Min value -21.9037

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 902
Mean -2.90885
Standard dev 0.648963
Max value -1.12576
Min value -4.77789

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 902
Mean 0.166413
Standard dev 0.371635
Max value 1.18378
Min value -0.775879

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 902
Mean 20.7001
Standard dev 0.649205
Max value 22.2642
Min value 19.4154

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 8.08185

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 902
Mean 160.182
Standard dev 0.677493
Max value 161.371
Min value 155.362

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 189.755

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems. Pitch and yaw are only displayed for flight A480, where specific manoeuvres were used to test the response of the NO_x inlets.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument "the fluorescence water vapour sensor".

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm³) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μ m to 3.00 μ m, to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μ m diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **CO:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_4 j_4 [O_3][H_2O]) / (k_5 [M] (j_6 + k_7 + [OH] k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + hv \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + hv \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4 , j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Laura Cardenas (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters were not recorded on MRF's data recording system and are therefore not available as part of this data summary. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **PAN ECGC's:** Data are not included in this report but will be made available at a later date. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).

ARASF

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